

Genomic analysis of the emergence and evolution of multidrug resistance during a *Klebsiella pneumoniae* outbreak including carbapenem and colistin resistance

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Objectives: To characterize at the genomic level the evolution of multiresistance during an outbreak of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in a burns intensive care unit. The outbreak involved a DHA-1 β -lactamase-producing strain that later acquired carbapenem and fosfomycin resistance, and in one case colistin resistance.

Methods: The genomes of two isolates were sequenced and compared with a previously sequenced genome. The role of hypermutability was investigated by measuring the mutation frequencies of the isolates and comparison with a collection of control strains.

Results: Sequence comparison identified four single-nucleotide variants and two transposon insertions. Analysis of the variants in the whole collection related carbapenem and fosfomycin resistance to a nonsense mutation in the *ompK36* porin gene and colistin resistance to an IS1 insertion in the *mgrB* gene. The plasmid carrying the *bla*_{DHA-1} gene was unstable in the absence of antibiotics, and analysis of isolates that had lost the plasmid showed that the porin mutation alone was not sufficient to generate carbapenem resistance. The mutation frequencies were similar among all the strains analysed.

Conclusions: Carbapenem resistance required production of the DHA-1 β -lactamase and decreased permeability, but fosfomycin resistance depended only on permeability. Resistance to colistin might be related to an alteration in the regulation of the *phoPQ* system. Hypermutation is not related to the selection of porin mutants. Plasmid instability might be due to the high number of mobile elements and suggests a major role for antibiotic selection pressure in the emergence and evolution of this outbreak.

Keywords: antibiotic resistance, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* genome, hypermutation, outbreak genomics

Introduction

The plasmid-encoded AmpC-type β -lactamases are clinically relevant cephalosporinases found mainly in *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. They confer resistance to a broad spectrum of β -lactams, are not blocked by common β -lactamase inhibitors and may confer resistance to carbapenems in strains with reduced permeability.¹ The genes are often borne by self-transmissible or mobilizable plasmids that gather several antibiotic

resistance genes, making effective treatment of infections very complicated. Strains with AmpC plasmids have been associated with nosocomial or healthcare environments, and the major risk factors for infection with these strains include long hospital stay, catheter use and previous antibiotic treatment.¹

In 2008, several DHA-1-producing *K. pneumoniae* isolates were found in clinical samples received from an intensive care unit (ICU). After several months, resistance to carbapenems, fosfomycin and colistin developed. To study the emergence of multidrug resistance

during this outbreak we characterized the isolates, sequenced three of them and investigated the role of hypermutability in the emergence of resistance.

Methods

Microbiological methods

Antibiotic susceptibility testing was done with the Wider[®] (Fco. Soria Melguizo, Madrid, Spain) or Vitek[®] (bioMérieux, Marcy-l'Étoile, France) systems and interpreted according to the CLSI,² except for tigecycline, for which EUCAST guidelines were followed.³ Carbapenemase production was studied by the modified Hodge test, and metallo-β-lactamase production by EDTA inhibition tests.

Mutation frequencies

Cells from overnight cultures (10^2 – 10^3) were inoculated in 5 mL of Luria Bertani (LB) broth and grown overnight. Aliquots from serial dilutions were plated onto LB agar plates with and without antibiotic (rifampicin or meropenem at 200 mg/L and 8 mg/L, respectively). Colony counting was performed after 24 h. Experiments were done in triplicate from independent colonies. Forty-five *K. pneumoniae* isolates collected during 2012 from community-acquired urinary tract infections and having wild-type susceptibility patterns were used to determine background mutation frequencies. *E. coli* K12 strain MG1655 was included as control.

Analysis of outer membrane proteins

Cells from 3 mL overnight cultures were sonicated and outer membrane proteins were extracted and analysed by SDS-PAGE.⁴

Molecular methods

Clonality was studied by repetitive sequence-based PCR using the Diversi-Lab system (bioMérieux). Multilocus sequence typing was based on the published *K. pneumoniae* scheme.⁵

Screening for AmpC β-lactamase, extended-spectrum β-lactamase and carbapenemase genes was done by PCR.^{6,7} The presence of the plasmids was studied by PCR of *repB* genes.

Genome sequencing and sequence analysis

KpQ15 and KpQ24 were sequenced from two shotgun libraries generated using a GS Titanium Sequencing Kit in a Roche 454 GS-FLX Sequencer (Life-sequencing S.L., Valencia, Spain). The KpQ15 sequencing yielded 112 contigs, with 5383954 bp, an N50 of 165515 bp and a peak depth of 27.0. The KpQ24 sequencing yielded 198 contigs, with 5405259 bp, an N50 of 79286 bp and a peak depth of 16.0. These whole genome shotgun projects have been deposited at DDBJ/EMBL/GenBank under the accession numbers AWOM00000000 (KpQ15) and AWON00000000 (KpQ24). The versions described in this paper are AWOM01000000 and AWON01000000, respectively. GS Reference Mapper 2.5 was used to compare the KpQ15 and KpQ24 genomes with the KpQ3 genome.

Results

Outbreak features

Between April 2008 and June 2009, 26 multidrug-resistant *K. pneumoniae* isolates were obtained from 20 patients in the burns ICU at our hospital. The patients had severe conditions, as indicated by APACHE II and Abbreviated Burn Severity Index (ABSI) scores, and long hospital and ICU stays, and most of them had received previous antibiotic treatments (Table 1). The isolates

(named KpQ1 to KpQ26) were obtained from blood (13), urine (7), burn wounds (2), bronchoalveolar lavage fluids (2), catheters (1) and tracheal fluid (1). One isolate was obtained from 16 patients, two isolates from 2 patients and three isolates from another 2 patients. Clonal analysis by repetitive sequence-based PCR showed that 25 of the isolates were clonally related, and multilocus sequence typing showed that they belonged to ST37. The single unrelated isolate was not further studied.

The clonal isolates were resistant to several β-lactams, including ceftazidime (Table 2), suggesting the presence of a plasmidic AmpC-type β-lactamase, which was identified as *bla*_{DHA-1} by PCR and sequencing. The *bla*_{SHV-11} and *bla*_{OXA-1} genes were also found.

In October 2008, a carbapenem-resistant isolate (KpQ15) was obtained from a urinary tract infection. The patient had received meropenem treatment for 13 days prior to recovery of the isolate. Most of the isolates obtained after this were resistant to carbapenems and fosfomycin. Carbapenemase production was negative and carbapenemase genes were not detected. Analysis of outer membrane proteins showed the loss of the OmpK36 porin (Figure 1) and sequencing the *ompK36* gene showed a point mutation (C508T) producing a premature stop codon (Q170Stop). The same mutation was found in all the carbapenem-resistant isolates. OmpK35 was not detected in membrane fractions of these isolates and sequencing of the *ompK35* gene promoter and coding regions did not find any mutation.

In February 2009, a carbapenem-resistant isolate (KpQ20) was obtained from blood cultures of one patient. It was susceptible to colistin and amikacin, and colistin treatment was initiated. Eleven days later a colistin-resistant isolate (KpQ24) was obtained from a urine culture of the same patient.

Genome sequencing

The genomes of KpQ15 and KpQ24 were sequenced and compared with that of the previously sequenced KpQ3⁸ (see the Supplementary data available at JAC Online). Four single-nucleotide variants were found and investigated in all the isolates by PCR and

Table 1. Patient data; *n* = 20

Gender, %	
male	84
female	16
Age (years), mean ± SD	54.9 ± 16.8
Burn body surface area (%), mean ± SD	37.32 ± 20.06
APACHE index, mean ± SD	14 ± 6
ABSI	
mean ± SD	8.7 ± 2.1
patients with ≥ 7, %	88.9
Days in ICU, mean ± SD	45.4 ± 22.8
Hospitalization days, mean ± SD	58.2 ± 41.9
Days with mechanical ventilation, mean ± SD	29.2 ± 23.4
Died, <i>n</i> (%)	6 (31.6)
Previous antibiotic treatment, <i>n</i> (%)	17 (89.5)
carbapenems	9 (47.4)
β-lactams	3 (15.8)
aminoglycosides	14 (73.7)
quinolones	7 (36.8)

Table 2. Antibiotic susceptibility profiles of some selected isolates, including the three sequenced isolates and their rifampicin-susceptible derivatives

	KpQ3		KpQ3 (rifampicin susceptible)		KpQ15		KpQ15 (rifampicin susceptible)		KpQ24		KpQ24 (rifampicin susceptible)		KpQ16-1		KpQ16-2	
Plasmid pKQ81	+		+		+		+		+		+		+			-
Plasmid pKQ57	+		-		+		-		+		-		+			-
DHA-1 gene	+		-		+		-		+		-		-			-
OXA-1 gene	+		-		+		-		+		-		+			-
Amoxicillin/ampicillin	≥32	R	≥32	R	≥32	R	≥32	R	≥32	R	≥32	R	>16	R	>16	R
Amoxicillin/clavulanic acid	≥32	R	≤2	S	≥32	R	4	S	≥32	R	8	S	≥32	R	≤2	S
Piperacillin/tazobactam	≥128	R	8	S	≥128	R	8	S	≥128	R	8	S	≥128	R	8	S
Cefuroxime	≥64	R	4	S	≥64	R	32	R	≥64	R	32	R	>16	R	8	S
Cefoxitin	≥64	R	≤4	S	≥64	R	≥64	R	≥64	R	≥64	R	≤4	S	≤8	S
Ceftazidime	≥64	R	≤1	S	≥64	R	≤1	S	≥64	R	≤1	S	≤1	S	≤1	S
Cefotaxime	≥64	R	≤1	S	≥64	R	≤1	S	≥64	R	≤1	S	≤1	S	≤1	S
Cefepime	2	R	≤1	S	≥64	R	≤1	S	≥64	R	≤1	S	4	S	≤1	S
Imipenem	≤0.25	S	≤0.25	S	>32	R	0.5	S	>32	R	0.5	S	≤0.25	S	≤0.25	S
Meropenem	≤1	S	≤1	S	8	R	≤1	S	8	R	≤1	S	≤1	S	≤1	S
Ertapenem	1	I	0.032	S	>32	R	1	I	>32	R	1	I	0.5	S	0.5	S
Gentamicin	8	I	≥16	R	≥16	R	≥16	R	≥16	R	≥16	R	≤2	S	≤2	S
Tobramycin	≥16	R	≥16	R	≥16	R	≥16	R	≥16	R	≥16	R	≥16	R	≤2	S
Amikacin	16	S	≤8	S	16	S	≤8	S	16	S	≤8	S	16	S	≤8	S
Nalidixic acid	≥32	R	≥32	R	≥32	R	≥32	R	≥32	R	≥32	R	>16	R	>16	R
Ciprofloxacin	≥4	R	≥4	R	≥4	R	≥4	R	≥4	R	≥4	R	>4	R	>4	R
Trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole	>4/76	R	>4/76	R	>4/76	R	>4/76	R	>4/76	R	>4/76	R	≤2/38	S	≤2/38	S
Fosfomycin	≤16	S	≤16	S	>1024	R	>1024	R	>1024	R	>1024	R	≤16	S	≤16	S
Tigecycline	1	S	≤0.5	S	≤0.5	S	≤0.5	S	1	S	≤0.5	S	2	I	≤0.5	S
Colistin	0.5	S	0.5	S	0.5	S	0.5	S	4	R	2	S	0.5	S	0.5	S

+, plasmid or gene present; -, plasmid or gene absent; S, susceptible; I, intermediate; R, resistant.

KpQ16-1 is a derivative of KpQ16 that lacks the DHA-1 gene but retains the plasmid.

KpQ16-2 is a derivative of KpQ16 that lacks the two plasmids.

Figure 1. SDS-PAGE analysis of outer membrane fractions obtained from overnight cultures of two of the sequenced isolates. KpQ3 is carbapenem susceptible and KpQ15 is carbapenem resistant.

sequencing. Two were non-silent mutations in hypothetical genes of unknown function (C to T producing R140G in *yecE*, nucleotide position 2102598, and C to T producing S73C in B819_98380, nucleotide position 4949113) and were exclusive of KpQ3. The third variant was the mutation in the *ompK36* gene found in the carbapenem-resistant isolates (nucleotide position 1815972). The fourth variant, a non-silent point mutation in the *sufB* gene (T to C producing S282P, nucleotide position 2368866), was found only in KpQ24. In addition, KpQ24 had two chromosomal copies of IS1, one in the intergenic region upstream of the *slt* gene (*slt::IS1*) and the other in a locus homologous to the *mgrB* gene (*mgrB::IS1*; *mgrB* is in positions 2144778–2144924 of GenBank sequence NZ_JH930400.1). The *mgrB::IS1* insertion was not found in any other isolate, while the *slt::IS1* insertion was found in the KpQ24 ancestor KpQ20 and in isolate KpQ19, obtained 1 day before KpQ20 from another patient.

Measurement of mutation frequencies

To investigate if the porin mutation had arisen in the context of high mutation levels, mutation frequencies were measured in all the isolates. Rifampicin, fluoroquinolones and streptomycin could not be used because the isolates were resistant. No rifampicin resistance mutations were found in the *rpoB* gene but there was a rifampin-ADP-ribosyltransferase gene (*arr-3*)⁹ in pKQ57. This plasmid was easily lost during subculturing, and the cells without the plasmid were susceptible to rifampicin. A collection of rifampicin-susceptible derivatives of the clinical isolates was therefore selected and used to measure mutation frequencies in rifampicin selection experiments. All the rifampicin-susceptible KpQ strains had similar frequencies, with an average of 2.8×10^{-8} mutants/total colony count (median: 1.9×10^{-8} ; range: 3.0×10^{-9} – 1.1×10^{-7}). The control strains had an average frequency of 7.3×10^{-8} (median: 2.8×10^{-8} ; range: 3.6×10^{-9} – 7.3×10^{-7}) (Figure 2).

The frequency of mutation to carbapenem resistance in the original (rifampicin resistant) carbapenem-susceptible KpQ isolates was measured using meropenem plates. No meropenem-resistant mutants were obtained from the rifampicin-susceptible strains, or

Figure 2. Frequencies of mutation to rifampicin and meropenem resistance in *K. pneumoniae*. The boxplot shows the median (central dot), IQR (box) and total range (lines) of the mutation frequencies measured. KpQ-rif is the frequency of mutation to rifampicin resistance in the 24 KpQ derivatives that had lost the pKQ57 plasmid, ctrl-rif is the frequency of mutation to rifampicin resistance in a collection of 45 *K. pneumoniae* isolates from community-acquired urinary tract infections and KpQ-mero is the frequency of mutation to meropenem resistance in the 15 KpQ carbapenem-susceptible clinical isolates.

from rifampicin-resistant derivatives of isolate KpQ16 that had lost the DHA-1 gene. For the remaining strains, the average mutation frequency was 2.0×10^{-7} (median: 1.7×10^{-7} ; range: 2.9×10^{-8} – 6.2×10^{-7}). PCR analysis of the *ompK36* gene in 59 mutants showed that 12 (20.3%) had IS1 insertions and one (1.7%) had a deletion. Six of the remaining 46 were sequenced and shown to have non-silent point mutations. All the mutants selected by meropenem were also resistant to fosfomycin.

Discussion

We present a *K. pneumoniae* ST37 outbreak that started with high-level resistance to β -lactams due to the production of an AmpC-type β -lactamase. During the course of the outbreak, a porin-deficient mutant resistant to carbapenems emerged and displaced the carbapenem-susceptible strain. In a single case, colistin resistance developed during colistin treatment. *K. pneumoniae* ST37 has a worldwide distribution and is relatively common in healthcare-related environments. DHA-1-producers belonging to ST37 have been described in France¹⁰ and Spain.¹¹

Carbapenem resistance depended on both the porin mutation and the DHA-1 β -lactamase. The mutant was also resistant to fosfomycin and this was independent of the plasmid (Table 2). Comparison of the genome sequences of KpQ3 and KpQ15 did not find other mutations that might be responsible for fosfomycin resistance. This was unexpected because fosfomycin resistance has not previously been associated with the loss of the OmpK36 porin.¹² Furthermore, we found that the meropenem-resistant porin mutants obtained *in vitro* from KpQ isolates were resistant to fosfomycin; this does not happen with other strains tested (OXA-48-producing *K. pneumoniae* belonging to ST11 or ST405),¹³ so this is a strain-specific phenotype.

The single colistin-resistant isolate had an IS1 insertion in the *mgrB* gene. The *mgrB* gene product is a feedback inhibitor of the *phoPQ* system, the deletion of which in *Salmonella typhimurium* induces an increase in PhoP-regulated transcription.¹⁴ Colistin resistance has been associated with the loss of *phoQ* function¹⁵ and with increased *phoP* expression,¹⁶ suggesting that in KpQ24, colistin resistance might result from the lack of *mgrB* gene product.

The sequenced genomes were found to be stable within the timeframe of the outbreak, since only four point mutations were found among the three isolates, despite their being obtained several months apart. This is probably related to the fact that the dissemination mechanism of *K. pneumoniae* involves very small infectious doses, generating population bottlenecks that select the most frequent genotype in every new colonization step. In particular, selection of the carbapenem-resistant mutant is likely to have been a strong population bottleneck. Besides, all the KpQ isolates had mutation frequencies similar to those of a control set of strains, implying that the selection of resistance mutations during the outbreak was not related to a hypermutation phenotype. This agrees with previous work showing that hypermutability is uncommon among clinical isolates of *K. pneumoniae*.¹⁷

The large plasmids, and in particular the one encoding the DHA-1 β -lactamase, were found to be unstable *in vitro*. The two plasmids contain several mobile elements, including 21 transposase genes. The transposases might have played a central role in the recruitment of drug resistance genes to the plasmids, but the accumulation of mobile elements could promote genetic rearrangements of the plasmid backbones, which may have compromised their stability. This suggests a predominant role for antibiotic selection pressure in plasmid maintenance during the course of this outbreak.

Note added in proof

Recently published work describes insertional inactivation of *mgrB* as a mechanism of colistin resistance in carbapenemase-producing *K. pneumoniae*.¹⁸

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Transparency declarations

J. M. has received research support from Roche Diagnostics Spain. M. M. is an employee of Era7 Bioinformatics Spain. R. T. and E. P. are employees and shareholders of Era7 Bioinformatics Spain. I. J. S. and M. A.-T. are employees of Roche Diagnostics Spain. F. M. C. is an employee of Lifesequencing S.L. All other authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Supplementary data

Supplementary data are available at JAC Online (<http://jac.oxfordjournals.org/>).

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